

RISK MATRIX – AN INNOVATIVE MANAGEMENT TOOL FOR SME`S

Author(s)*: Calin-Dumitru POP, Nicolae UNGUREANU, Adrian Dan POP
Position: PhD Student, Prof. PhD, PhD Student,
University: Technical University of Cluj-Napoca
Address: Baia Mare, Dr. Victor Babes Str., No. 62A, Romania
Email: calin.pop@cunbm.utcluj.ro, nicolae.ungureanu@cunbm.utcluj.ro,
adriandanpop@gmail.com
Webpage: <http://www.utcluj.ro/>

Abstract

Purpose – increasing the survival rate of SMEs.

Methodology/approach – an analysis of the socio-economic framework for the North-West development region of Romania using a mixed research, both qualitatively and quantitatively through the survey method – questionnaire and the analysis and the interpretation of information from the National Office of the Trade Register.

Findings – there are signs that the total number of SMEs in the North-West development region of Romania will decrease. In addition, half of the SMEs that participated in the survey do not use management tools to meet the company's objectives.

Research limitations/implications – the risk matrix do not eliminate risk, but rather prioritizes the appropriate use of resources and time and facilitate the decision-making.

Practical implications – SMEs do not have an entire arsenal of strategic weapons and are often led by the owner-manager who runs the risk of failure following their own ideologies and practices.

Originality/value – the use of a risk matrix – an innovative management tool for SMEs with which the management (entrepreneur) will identify and quantify the risks to which the company is exposed, will increase the survival chance of SMEs.

Key words: Risk Matrix.

Introduction

In Romania, from December 1990 until March 2017, over two point eight million businesses were set up, of which one point thirty-two million were closed in the meantime; the survival rate of a business is fifty-two point seven, meaning only one out of two businesses manage to remain on the market, according to data (ONRC 2019) for the last 25 years.

The latest analysis on the demography of enterprises conducted by the National Institute of Statistics in Romania, was conducted for the period 2010 - 2014 and reveals that approximately only fifty point nine percent of newly created enterprises in Romania are active four years after establishment, given that at the EU level, the highest four-year survival rate is in Finland, where over seventy percent of start-ups in 2010 were active in 2014 as well.

According to Welsh, White and Dowell (1981), small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) contribute to economic growth - the positive correlation between the level of development of the small and medium-sized enterprise sector and the gross domestic product (GDP) of an economy, contributes to reducing unemployment and increasing living standards - provides jobs, and last but not least according to Nicolescu (2008), it plays the role of stabilizer on the market due to their prompt reaction to change – prompt reaction due to the flexible structure that gives them adaptability.

The role that small and medium-sized enterprises play in both developing and developed countries cannot be ignored and, therefore, their existence and survival it is a matter of major interest for both policy makers and researchers; countless SMEs cease to operate within a year of their establishment.

Theoretical background

Most people want to avoid risk however, the economy encourages businesses to take risks. Business operations, the activities of extracting capital from one source to another, literally mean taking risks for higher profits. Moreover, taking risks in one way or another brings competition and innovation.

Leopoulos, Kirytopoulos and Malandrakis (2006) warn managers - owners of SMEs, to be aware of potential risks, to be familiar with risk identification and risk mitigation, or may suffer catastrophic consequences. Moreover, St-Pierre and Bahri (2006) states that SMEs face difficulties in obtaining financing due to the high level of risk and the insufficient level of profitability associated with them.

In every enterprise we are dealing with risk management, but not always in a completely transparent, repeatable or permanent way that supports the decision-making process.

There are several important ERM (Enterprise Risk Management) models, each of which describes an approach to identifying, analyzing, responding to and monitoring the risks and opportunities, both internally and externally, that the company faces.

Starting from the analysis of COSO ERM and ISO 31000 models - being the most widespread and debated in the literature - I believe that the use of a functional matrix - an innovative management tool for SMEs can be the solution that will increase survival rates of SMEs.

Risk matrices have two main applications. First, when used in making decisions about accepting risk; secondly, to prioritize risks - which risk must be addressed first.

At the same time, the risk matrix will ensure the following:

- prompt reaction - must be easy to apply by the management (manager - employer)
- low costs - not to represent a financial burden
- friendly interface - data entry without requiring extensive specialized knowledge (economic - financial, computer systems, etc.).

Methodology

In order to collect the information needed for the study which will identify the need and reliability of using the risk matrix in SMEs, a mixed research was conducted, both qualitatively and quantitatively by the method of the Questionnaire and the analysis and interpretation of information from the National Trade Register Office.

Firstly, the socio-economic framework of the functioning of SMEs was analyzed - the analysis and interpretation of the situation of SMEs in the North West Region of Romania for the period 2017-2019, for the 6 counties that make up the region: Bihor, Bistrița – Năsăud, Cluj, Maramureș, Satu Mare and Sălaj.

The following statistical data for the North-West region, which are of interest for the topic addressed, were analyzed and interpreted:

- active professionals – all enterprises registered in the Trade Register and which are not in any of the states that may cause the loss of legal personality,
- new registrations – the total number of enterprises that were set up at the Trade Register during the analyzed period
- closures – all the companies disbanded for the analyzed period,

for the years 2017-2019, in order to present the evolution and situation of the last three years.

Secondly, the data collected using the questionnaire - *Improving management tools for SMEs* - applied to owners (entrepreneurs) or staff involved in the day-to-day management activities of the enterprise with a minimum of 3 years from the establishment were interpreted. The questionnaire was chosen as

the survey method, it is considered according to de Singly, Blanchet, Gotman and Kaufmann (1998) and Jemna (2018) the basic tool of the opinion poll.

The questionnaire includes questions on the profile of the entrepreneur and the activity carried out within the SMEs, product and market identification, business management, labor force and last but not least, the evolution of the business in terms of decisions and factors that influenced the business.

From the searching techniques, Şandor (2013) the following variants were selected:

- face to face - the interaction between the operator and the respondent - the operator reads the questions and notes the answers of the subjects
- self-administered questionnaire - the researcher distributes the questions and the subjects answer them and then the researcher then collects the answers.

In the introductory part of the questionnaire the purpose of the research was specified, the subjects are assured of data confidentiality, the enterprise is identified, the category (medium, small or micro) and the quality of the respondent (owner, involved in daily management activities of the enterprise).

The questions in the questionnaire were formulated using accessible and clear language.

The answer options were formulated and presented to be as clear and complete as possible, avoiding multiple variants as much as possible.

The extracted qualitative and quantitative data were analyzed with the statistical data analysis programs SPSS 20 and EXCEL.

Results and discussion

First, I analyzed the following indicators: new registrations, closures, active professionals and dynamics of the socio-economic environment of SMEs in the North-West region of Romania for the period 2017-2019.

The analysis for the period 2017-2019 for the North-West region regarding the registrations, closures and the total of active professionals, was performed for the following categories of enterprises: Joint Stock Company (SA), Limited Liability Company (SRL), Authorized Individual (PFA) , Debutant Limited Liability Company (SRL-D), Individual Enterprise (II), Family Enterprise (IF) and Limited Partnership (SC). The mentioned categories were selected because they represent over 99% of the total registrations for the selected period.

Legally active professionals are professionals registered in the Trade Register who have not declared their suspension of activity and are not in any of the conditions that can cause the loss of legal personality, Armanu (2018). This eliminates the enterprises in bankruptcy, dissolution, liquidation, insolvency, judicial reorganization, with temporary suspension of activity.

Analyzing the data collected from the National Office of the Trade Register, a synthetic statistical situation was prepared regarding the evolution of enterprises for the analyzed period, 2017 - 2019, North - West region of Romania, table no. 12. The summary situation is presented in table one.

Table 1. SME`s evolution 2017- 2019 N-V

	2017	2018	2019
New registrations	23155	23193	20478
Closures	11314	12188	15780
Active professionals	193348	204387	209961
Dynamics (new registrations - closures)	11841	11005	4698

The chart regarding the evolution and dynamics (new registrations – closures – total active professionals) of enterprises for the period 2017 - 2019, North - West region of Romania is presented chart one.

Chart one - the evolution of enterprises, N-V region period 2017-2019

The total number of professionals active during 2017-2019 for the development region of North-West of Romania has been increasing, but there are signs that the maximum number has been reached, and a period of decline is foreseen due to the fact that the number of closures was increasing from year to year and the number of registrations for the same period was decreasing. Moreover, in 2020 we face what Taleb (2018) has developed, namely the black swan theory; in this case it is the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, i.e. difficulties in specifying the consequences and possibly in the full specification of the event itself and how small and medium-sized enterprises will be affected.

Secondly, I resorted to interpreting the data collected from the total number of SMEs that completed the questionnaire. The main findings will be presented below.

About three quarters of entrepreneurs - staff involved in daily management activities are with higher education.

Of the respondents, half stated that they do not use management tools to achieve the company's objectives. This is also because eighty percent of enterprises (respondents) are represented by micro or small enterprises. While large firms have a whole arsenal of strategic weapons and even seek external advice on the risks facing the enterprise, micro and small enterprises need to manage their resources much more limited. Therefore, they cannot afford to allocate funds or hire specialized personnel in the field of risk management.

Another element that should be mentioned is the fact that seventy percent of those who participated in completing the questionnaire stated that they are not registered in an association or confederation in their field of activity.

Training in SMEs is oriented towards increasing income, most courses taken by entrepreneurs or employees being focused on the following areas: marketing, management and manufacturing - production. Very rarely do we have to deal with a management approach that aims at courses dedicated to risk management in the company. Moreover, eighty percent of respondents stated that they do not carry out risk management planning activities.

Of the total respondents to the questionnaire applied, in terms of the degree of readiness to deal with the risks faced by the company, and covering the following elements: identification, analysis, assessment, management and monitoring of risks, all stated that they identify risks but only sixty percent monitor them.

Half of SMEs do not use management tools to meet the company's objectives, but seventy percent of them said they would be willing to try.

Conclusion

There are several factors that could have a negative effect on the profitability, security and stability of the business. One of the main goals of every entrepreneur-owner is to identify these risks and prevent them before they become a major problem. Therefore, it is necessary to design a general picture that gives the management (entrepreneur - employer) a synthetic picture of the vulnerabilities of the company.

Regarding the feasibility of the proposed instrument – risk matrix, the following should be clarified: seventy percent of respondents have higher education as their educational training, which can be translated into their possibility and ability to develop their risk rankings according to the matrix, to identify the risks that represent the higher general (and therefore priority) threats.

The format of the matrix is given by the environment in conjunction with contextual elements (financial, human resources, marketing, quality, information systems, performance, etc.) in order to obtain a ranking of the level of risk for small and medium enterprises. Along with the proposed matrix, a response strategy template was developed for the identified and analyzed risks, which may include avoidance, reduction, alternative actions, acceptance, transfer, risk sharing, etc.

The management tool - risk matrix - will not give assurances that adverse events will not happen but provides the warning to ensure business continuity.

I believe that the results of the study justify the need for the management tool for SMEs, functional matrix - innovative management tool for understanding internal and external risks so that they are properly assumed and it will lead to profit maximization - the fundamental objective of the company.

References

Armanu, L.

2018

Disciplina financiară în domeniul operațiunilor cu numerar” Editura: Etnous, București

Jemna, D., V.

2018

Sandajul statistic” Editura: Alexandru Ioan Cuza, Iași

Leopoulus, V., Kirytopoulos, K., and Malandrakis, C.

2006

Risk management for SME`s: Tools to use and how” In Production, Planning & Control

Nicolescu, O., Nicolescu, C.

2008

Intreprenoriatul și managementul întreprinderilor” Editura: Economică, București

de Singly, F., Blanchet. A., Gotman, A., and Kaufmann, J., C.

1998

Ancheta și metodele ei: chestionarul, interviul de producere a datelor, interviul comprehensiv” Editura: Polirom, Iași

St-Pierre, J., and Bahri, M.

2006

The use of the accounting beta as an overall risk indicator for unlisted companies.

Șandor, S., D.

2013

Metode și tehnici de cercetare în științele sociale” Editura: Tritonic, București

Taleb, N., N.

2018

Lebăda neagră” Editura: Curtea Veche, București

ONRC – Oficiul Național Registrul Comerț (National Trade Register Office)

2020

<https://www.onrc.ro/index.php/ro/>

Welsh, J., A. White, J., F. and Dowell, P.

1981

A small Business is not a Little Big Business” In Harvard Business Review: July/August, p 18

Risk matrix

		CONSEQUENCES				
		INSIGNIFICANT does not pose a significant threat	MINOR potential negative consequences, insignificant impact	MODERATE considerable negative consequences, significant impact	CRITICAL substantial negative consequences and significant impact	DEZASTUOS extreme negative consequences, top priority
PROBABILITY	UNLIKELY extremely rare, almost no probability of occurrence	LOW 1 - 1	LOW 1 - 2	LOW 1 - 3	MEDIUM 1 - 4	MEDIUM 1 - 5
	RARE unusual, but with a small chance of manifestation	LOW 2 - 1	LOW 2 - 2	MEDIUM 2 - 3	HIGH 2 - 4	HIGH 2 - 5
	OCCASIONAL typical, with a chance of occurrence of 50/50	LOW 3 - 1	MEDIUM 3 - 2	HIGH 3 - 3	HIGH 3 - 4	EXTREME MELY 3 - 5
	PROBABLE likely to occur	MEDIUM 4 - 1	HIGH 4 - 2	HIGH 4 - 3	EXTREME MELY 4 - 4	EXTREME MELY 4 - 5
	DEFINITELY it is almost certain	MEDIUM 5 - 1	HIGH 5 - 2	EXTREME MELY 5 - 3	EXTREME MELY 5 - 4	EXTREME MELY 5 - 5

Strategy template response

NAME		Objective	
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REF/ID	PRE-MITIGATION				DEPARTMENT / LOCATION	MITIGATIONS / WARNINGS / REMEDIES	POST-MITIGATION			
	RISK	THE SEVERITY OF THE RISK	RISK PROBABILITY	RISK LEVEL			THE SEVERITY OF THE RISK	RISK PROBABILITY	RISK LEVEL	ACCEPTABLE?
		MINOR	RAR	MEDIUM			INSIGNIFICANT	LESS PROBABLE	LOW	GA
		MODERATE	OCCASIONAL	MIDDLE			MINOR	RAR	LOW	GA
		CRITICAL	PROBABLE	HIGH			MODERATE	OCCASIONAL	MEDIUM	R
		DEZASTUOS	DEFINITE	EXTREMELY			CRITICAL	PROBABLE	HIGH	GU

GA - generally acceptable
R - reasonably
GU - generally unacceptable